

PROSPECTS FOR THE USE OF ESSENTIAL OIL FROM FILIPENDULOUS YARROW RAW MATERIALS

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Relevance. *Filipendulous yarrow* (*Achillea filipendulina* Lam.) is a perennial herbaceous plant widely distributed in Central and Southwest Asia. Plants of the *Achillea* genus have traditionally been used in folk and modern medicine due to their high content of biologically active compounds. Of particular interest is the essential oil of *A. filipendulina*, which exhibits antibacterial, antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory effects. Despite the widespread use of the *Achillea* genus, the essential oil of *A. filipendulina* remains insufficiently studied, which determines the relevance of its investigation.

Objective of the study: To conduct a literature review on the composition and pharmacological potential of the essential oil of *Achillea filipendulina*, as well as to outline the prospects for its application in medicine and pharmacy.

Materials and methods: The work is based on the analysis of published studies on the phytochemical composition and biological activity of the essential oil of *Achillea filipendulina*. The following publications served as the main sources: In the study by S. Asnaashari et al., results were presented demonstrating the wide range of biological activities of *A. filipendulina* essential oil. The authors identified pronounced antioxidant and antimalarial properties; in addition, the oil showed inhibitory activity against the enzyme xanthine oxidase, highlighting the prospects for further pharmacological investigation of the plant. The review by A.A. Manassova et al. summarized data on the use of *Achillea* species in traditional medicine. It was established that yarrow has traditionally been applied in ethnopharmaceutical practice as an anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and antioxidant agent. A study by the Iranian author N. Salehi was devoted to a detailed analysis of the chemical profile of essential oils obtained from different plant organs (stems, leaves, flowers). The results showed that the oils are characterized by a high content of monoterpenes, while the proportion of sesquiterpenes was significantly lower, confirming the leading role of monoterpene compounds in shaping the phytochemical profile. Thus, the analysis of data from different authors made it possible to combine information on the chemical composition, biological activity, and traditional use of *A. filipendulina*, providing a more comprehensive understanding of its pharmacological potential.

Results: According to the literature, the essential oil of *Achillea filipendulina* contains a significant amount of terpene compounds (mono- and sesquiterpenes) with antioxidant and antimicrobial activity. Promising directions for the use of the oil as a natural source of substances with anti-inflammatory and antibacterial effects have been identified.

Conclusion: The essential oil of filipendulous yarrow is a promising subject for further research. Its chemical composition and pharmacological potential make it a valuable source of biologically active compounds of practical importance for medicine and pharmacy. This study was carried out within the framework of the intramural grant of Asfendiyarov KazNMU "Development

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of technology and standardization of pharmaceutical products based on kaolinite clays and essential oils of medicinal plants.”